

DEVELOPMENT, STRUCTURE, TOPOGRAPHY, PATHOPHYSIOLOGY, FUNCTIONS AND REGENERATION OF THE HUMAN LIVER

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the development, structure, topography, pathophysiology, functions, regeneration of the liver.

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Hepatology is the science of the liver. The liver (Hepar) is the largest gland in the body and weighs 1,500 grams in an adult.

Liver development begins at 3 weeks of embryogenesis when the ventral wall of the middle intestinal tract ectoderm (liver bay) sinks into the abdomen. During development, the hepatic bladder is divided into upper cranial and lower caudal sections. From the cranial part develops the liver and hepatic ducts, from the caudal part develops the gallbladder and its excretory ducts. Liver structure: The surface of the liver is covered with a fibrous membrane (Glisson's capsule) consisting of a dense connective tissue that is tightly attached to the peritoneum by a visceral sheet. The liver parenchyma is made up of pieces of liver. The classic sections of the liver are polygonal prism-shaped structures with a width not exceeding 1.5 mm, separated from each other by thin interstitial connective tissue. Therefore, the boundaries of the liver are not clearly defined. The liver parenchyma is mainly composed of 80% of hepatocytes, 20% of endothelial cells and macrophages. Chemical composition of the liver:

- Water 70-75%
- Proteins 12-24%
- Lipids - 2-6%
- Glycogen 2-8%

- Iron 0.02%
- Phospholipid 1.5-3%
- Triacylglyceride consists of 1.2-2%.

Liver topography: According to galatopia, the liver is located in the upper layer of the abdominal cavity, the main part is located under the right ribs. The average person is 20-22 cm long, 10-12 cm wide and 7-8 cm thick. According to skeletal topography, the apex of the liver extends from 4-5 ribs on the right and 5 ribs to 11 ribs on the left. The lower border is located along the rib cage. According to the syntopia, the liver is anterior diaphragm, anterior abdominal wall, upper diaphragm, posterior esophagus, inferior vena cava, abdominal aorta, inferior vena cava, gallbladder, inner surface of the spleen on the left side, abdomen on the right located on the side wall. Specificity of the liver in children: Blood, which is rich in oxygen and other substances necessary for the growth of the placenta, first passes through the liver of the fetus. Therefore, this organ develops faster than others. The relative size of a newborn's liver is almost twice that of an adult. Liver development lasts for 6-7 years. The histological structure of the liver of an 8-year-old child is almost no different from that of an adult. Babies develop bile very quickly. She weighs 4 times more than an adult in 1 kg body weight. bile secretion increases during growth. Although the amount of bile in a young child is sufficient, the quality is not good. Lots of bile acids, cholesterol, salts, mucins and pigments. There is also a difference in the ratio of bile acids. Children are high in tauroxol and adults are high in glycolic acid. In the first week of life, the bile contains almost no secondary bile acids (lithoxol, deoxychol). They only appear when germs invade the gut. The baby's liver is unable to synthesize enough bile acids because of the low absorption of fats. When the amount of bile acids in the small intestine is relatively low, the fat in the milk is not added to the micelles and excreted in the feces in the form of tri and monoglycerides. Within 1.5 months, the liver's ability to synthesize bile acids increases and the absorption of fats increases to 80-85%. Liver function: detoxification - metabolism and excretion of endogenous substrates, steroid and peptide hormones, indole and skatol formed in the intestine. In digestion - the formation of bile. In 1 day the liver produces 1000-1800ml o. The pH of the liver is 7.3-8.0. Bile contains 80% of glycoxol and 20% of tauroxol. Grass emulsifies fats, which increase the surface area of the lipase enzyme. Grass increases the activity of lipase enzymes. Increases the hydrolysis and absorption of proteins and carbohydrates. In metabolism: the synthesis of albumins all 13-18 g / day,

beta globulins 50%, blood clotting system proteins, urea is synthesized only in the liver, cholesterol, phospholipids synthesis, bilirubin metabolism.

Storage: The liver stores up to 600 ml of blood in its blood vessels, which is a storehouse of glycogen, A, B12, and iron. Synthetic: performs the functions of synthesis and storage of plasma proteins, creatine, urea, cholesterol.

Hematopoiesis: is a blood-forming organ in the embryonic period.

Protection: stellate reticuloendothelial cells (Cooper cells) located in the walls of sinusoidal capillaries are an important component of the mononuclear phagocytic system and phagocytose foreign substances entering the body.

During starvation: breaks down glycogen to meet the energy needs of the brain and glucose-dependent tissues. It is a device of gluconeogenesis to normalize the amount of glucose in the blood when it decreases.

Xenobiotics: substances (drugs, preservatives, toxins) that enter the body enterally and parenterally but are not used for plastic and energy purposes are neutralized by a smooth endoplasmic reticulum of hepatocytes.

Bilirubin metabolism: Bilirubin is a product of hem metabolism, which is formed mainly from the breakdown of erythrocytes, partly cytochromes and myoglobin. There are two types of bilirubin in the blood. Free and bound bilirubin. The liver produces about 300 mg of bound bilirubin per day, but a healthy liver is able to excrete 10 times more bound bilirubin. Increased total bilirubin concentration in the blood leads to the development of jaundice syndrome. Because bilirubin has the ability to yellow the skin, mucous membranes and sclera. Depending on the mechanism of development, we distinguish 3 types of jaundice:

- Hepatic jaundice (hemolytic);
- Cellular (observed in hepatocyte damage);
- Subhepatic (mechanical, obstetric - is observed in disorders of bile secretion).

In addition, there are physiological jaundice of newborns and hereditary disorders of bilirubin metabolism.

Liver Regeneration: The liver's ability to regenerate is very strong. Recovery at this rate is slowed by compensatory hypertrophy and mitotic division of hepatocytes. Experiments have shown that even when 75% of an animal's liver is removed, it quickly regains its original mass. Normal liver cell division is very low (0.3-0.9%). Only when the liver is injured does cell division accelerate.

References:

1. Axmedov .A.G. Rasulov X.A. "Anatomy" T.: "Ijod print" 2018.
2. Alyaviya O.T. Qodirov Sh.K. "Physiology" T .: "Navruz" 2019.

3. To'xtayev.Q.R. Azizova F.X. "Histology cytology embryology" T.: "Creative print" 2020.
4. Sabirova R.A. Yuldashev N.M "Biokimyo" T .: "Ijod print" 2020.
5. Kadyrov A. "Normal physiology" T. : "Abu Ali ibn Sino" 2017.
6. Sadriddinov A.F. "Short course of histology" T.: "Tashkent" 2020.
7. Tursunov.E.A. Collection of lectures on cytology and general histology "T.: Tashkent" 2018.
8. N.X.Shomurodov. Sh.M.Ahmedov "Clinical anatomy" T .: "Xilol media" 2020.
9. KA Agzamov "Practical manual from topographic anatomy" T.: "Tashkent ibn Sino" 2009.
10. S.A.Dolimov. AA Abdukarimov "Topographic anatomy" T .: "Tashkent Ibn Sino" 1992.

